

UNIVERSITY OF TURIN

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

The mechanisms put in place by Italian legislation¹ to combat harassment and promote equal opportunities in public workplaces, including academia, have seen their role slightly strengthened. Some universities and research organisations have also shared experiences in addressing the issue. The requirement to introduce Codes of Conduct that specifically refer to sexual harassment and to setting up a protection system involving the Guarantee Committee of Equal Opportunities (CUG)² and the confidential counsellor³ has helped to increase awareness of gender-based violence (GBV) and has ushered in concrete tools to fight the phenomenon. However, the lack of specific guidelines on how to draw up a Code of Conduct and to implement it in practice, without any independent body with control and coordinate functions, has resulted in a highly differentiated system of protection (Perini 2019). Another weakness has been the tendency to focus on the issue of gender equality rather than on GBV, minimising the gender component in addressing issues such as sexual harassment and gender discrimination. This has produced a formalised and technical approach and reduced the overall effectiveness of the system. Even though most Italian universities have introduced Codes of Conduct regarding harassment, there has never been any formal action taken against universities that have not yet complied with the national legislation, despite the fact that the Italian law provides for the possibility of sanctioning organisations that fail to do so. It is hard to estimate how many higher education institutions and research funding organisations in Italy have failed to comply with national regulations, since there is no specific body that can gather such data at the national level. As of December 2020, only 32 of 85 universities had instituted the position of a confidential counsellor within their protection system.⁴

¹ Legislative Decree No. 198/2006, Code of Equal Opportunities in the Workplace.

² A formal body with proposing, consulting, and verification functions for the development of a culture of equal opportunities and against discrimination.

³ The confidential counsellor helps victims of discrimination and harassment and, at the request of the person concerned, takes on the case and informs them of the most suitable way of dealing with it.

⁴ <https://www.visir.is/g/20171884043d>

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

The reference policy on GBV is the Code of Conduct of the University of Turin (2016) which is a policy not solely dedicated to GBV.⁵ The main actors are the CUG, the confidential counsellor, the general director, and the rector. In 2019, **an anti-violence listening desk** was established, the only one of its kind in Italy. The desk offers the services of listening, psychological support, and legal assistance to any woman who studies or works at the Unito. It is the result of collaboration between VARCO⁶ and the anti-violence centre E.M.M.A.⁷ and was founded by the CRT Foundation.⁸ The university makes space available for the listening desk once a week. In addition, there is a telephone number to contact. In collaboration with the operators of the desk, VARCO carries out, approximately every six months, an assessment of the activities.⁹ VARCO is working to encourage the opening of other offices in the more decentralised parts of the university. A complex system has thus been put in place for reporting, monitoring, and taking care of victims.

With respect to public controversy, on 12 February 2020 the 'Independent Students' collective distributed a questionnaire to students with the aim of quantitatively investigating the violence perceived within the university. The result was that 40% of female students declared that they had suffered from GBV or gender discrimination and 70% that they had suffered from body shaming. Moreover, only a small percentage of students (30%) stated that were aware of the activities of the CUG and three students out of ten said that they saw the university environment as unsafe. These striking results were published by the collective after some students were reported to have been sexually assaulted within the university. This news was reported in many local and national newspapers, which gave rise to an extensive debate on the situation at universities and on the effectiveness of the tools to combat GBV.

URLs

- › The Code of Conduct: https://www.unito.it/sites/default/files/decr_codice_comportamento_646_2016.pdf

Entry into force: 2016

⁵ Università di Torino. (2016). Codice di comportamento dell'università degli studi di Torino.

⁶ Varco: Violenza contro le donne: Azioni in Rete per prevenire e Contrastare - Violence against women: online actions to prevent and counter. Research Group of the Department of Culture, Politics and Society of the University of Turin. The aim is to build a sustainable and strategic organisational model to combat and prevent GBV through mapping of the professionals and the skills involved, of the critical issues and good practices. Founded by the CRT Foundation in 2019.

⁷ A non-profit association that manages, in Turin and Piedmont, some anti-violence centres where women victims of violence can turn to for listening and psychological assistance, legal advice, career orientation, social integration and development of skills.

⁸ Private non-profit philanthropic body that defines itself as the "engine" of development and growth in Piedmont and Aosta Valley in three macro-areas: art and culture, research and education, welfare and territory.

⁹ The monitoring will consider both quantitative data (flyers distributed, access for information requests, cases handled) and the qualitative notes and reflections of the operators. At the end of the year a public event will be organised for the presentation of the report on the activities.

TRAINING

In 2016-2017, the university collaborated on the international DAPHNE USVSV project with the goal of developing an **innovative training course aimed at university staff to teach them to respond appropriately to manifestations of sexual violence**. The university conducted and evaluated an experimental model of training involving 92 volunteers from the University of Turin and conducted a survey to understand the perception of harassment in the university environment. The Research Centre for Women's and Gender Studies (CIRSDe) was the responsible party. At the end, a report was produced as a tool for running training courses on prevention at universities. After this, a group of students asked CIRSDe to attend a meeting organised by them about sexual violence and homophobia.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

The university is a **centre of excellence for research on gender subjects**, with the CIRSDe as one of the main examples of such research in Italy. However, there is no structured training course in gender studies yet run by the university, and no specifications on mandatory subjects in the university curricula.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: Sexual harassment and gender-based harassment are addressed in the Code of Conduct.

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

7Ps covered: 4Ps are covered – protection, prosecution, provision of services and policy.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Intersectionality addressed

No

Specific vulnerable groups

Not defined

Target groups

The policy covers academic staff, non-academic staff, and students.

Bystanders addressed: Yes. The document states that everyone who operates within the university must contribute to ensuring a work environment in which the dignity of a person is respected, and specifies that each facility manager has a particular duty to monitor and, where possible, prevent the occurrence of sexual or moral harassment or discriminatory acts.

Role of perpetrators addressed: Yes. Article 9 directly mentions perpetrators and states that a first meeting for legal consultation is guaranteed by the university free of charge. In the event that a complaint proves to be unfounded, the administration undertakes to publicly rehabilitate the good name of the accused person.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: No.

Monitoring: No.

Evaluation: No.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

Yes.

The formal procedure distinguishes between technical administrative staff on the one hand and teaching staff, researchers, and students on the other. In the case of all other procedures and the application of the code there is one procedure for all.

The policy defines: Who to contact, how to report/file a formal complaint, a description of the investigation process, timeframe, responsible persons/units, outcomes.

Who to contact: A victim of harassment or discrimination can, through an informal procedure, file a written complaint with the confidential counsellor. Alternatively, through a formal procedure the victim can file a complaint with the director general (if the victim is a member of the technical administrative staff) or with the rector (if the victim is a student, a researcher, or a teacher).

How to report: Complaints, whether through the informal or the formal procedure, must be made in writing. The complainant must indicate whether the complaint is made in reference to the University Code of Conduct or the University Code of Ethics (2012). Although the latter does not explicitly refer to sexual harassment and only generally refers to gender discrimination, it nevertheless asserts that 'everyone has the right to be treated with equal respect and consideration

and not to be discriminated against on the basis of personal and social conditions such as: gender and sexual orientation, religion and personal beliefs, physical appearance and skin colour, language, ethnic origins, wealth and citizenship, age, position occupied in the university system - Art. 6). In the latter case, the procedure in the event of a formal complaint differs in some parts - see the entry on Responsible Persons.

Time frame: The policy indicates that complaints must be lodged within a reasonable period of time after the harassment occurred (approximately 60 days). Also, the duration of an informal procedure must not exceed 120 days from the time the incident was reported.

Description of the investigation: The text offers a brief description of the investigation process that the confidential counsellor is responsible for in the case of an informal procedure. The confidential counsellor can invite the person responsible for the harassment for an interview, collect evidence, and access the administrative documents relating to the case. There is no description of the disciplinary investigation process that general director or rector is responsible for in the case of a formal procedure.

Responsible Persons: The confidential counsellor is the person responsible for the informal procedure. In the case of the formal procedure, which can lead to disciplinary measures, the person in charge is the general director (for administrative staff) or the rector (for teaching staff, researchers, students). The document specifies that if a victim prefers to appeal to the Code of Ethics, the formal procedure must follow the scheme set out in Article 10 of the Code of Ethics. In this case, the complaint must be submitted to the competent teaching, research, or administrative unit, which sends the relevant documentation and a written statement from the accused to the rector. If the rector believes that the case has merit, then s/he ask the Academic Senate to rule on the case.

Outcomes: The objective of an informal procedure is to provide a victim of harassment or discrimination with the best possible advice and to try, where possible, to pursue a path of informal reconciliation, avoiding the path of a formal complaint. Achieving this end may require the transfer of staff, the organisation of conciliation meetings between the victim and the perpetrator, and more generally the adoption of 'whatever actions are appropriate in order to ensure a work environment that respects the freedom and dignity of people involved in the case'. In the case of a formal procedure, the outcome may be disciplinary sanctions.

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

Acknowledgment: *this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researcher Karla Nicole Brunello in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

